

INVESTIGATIONS ON INSTABILITY OF PERIODIC ORBITS OF NIGCOMSAT AROUND TRIANGULAR LAGRANGIAN POINTS IN THE EARTH-MOON SYSTEM WITH RADIATION PRESSURE AND VARIABLE MASSES

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Abstract: The Nigerian Space Agency launched the Nigerian Communication Satellites (NigComSat) into orbit in 2007. The satellite was designed to have a lifespan of 15 years and to remain in orbit for that duration. Unfortunately, after a year, the orbit became unstable and the satellite left orbit. In this paper, the focus is to investigate instability of the periodic orbits of the NigComSat around triangular Lagrangian points (TLPs) using the model of the restricted three-body problem with radiation pressure and variable masses. The masses of the host bodies are assumed to vary with time and the smaller body is a radiation emitter. We compute explicit expressions for the frequency, angle of rotation of the principal axis, eccentricity and lengths of semi-axes of the orbits of the satellite. Since some facts are not directly discernable from the analytic solutions, numerical evidences are provided to analyze the structure of the orbits, when the host bodies are assumed to be the Earth and Moon. Our numerical explorations reveal that due to the mass variation parameter, the orientation and paths around the TLPs differ and at some points, the NigComSat travels around the Earth and TLP while for some value of the mass variation parameter, the NigComSat does not travel around the TLP and the Earth. Further, as the mass variation increases the orbit flattens and the NigComSat leaves orbit. Further, the zero velocity curves around TLPs are explored and it is seen that the most significant perturbing effect is the mass variation of the main bodies. Additionally, when the Earth and Moon gain sufficient mass, large region becomes dynamically forbidden for the NigComSat and it leaves the vicinity of the TLPs and escape into space. Consequently, the NigComSat leaves the orbits due to the instabilities posed by the increasing mass of the Earth and the Moon coupled with the radiation pressure of the Moon. The orbits about Lagrangian points are important for scientific

investigations. Since, a number of space missions have been completed and some are being proposed by various space agencies.

Keywords: R3BP, Periodic orbit, NigComSat, Radiation Pressure, Triangular Lagrangian points variable masses

1 Introduction

The Three-body problem is an important problem in the classical and quantum mechanics which involves modeling the motion of three particles subject to their mutually gravitational attractions. The simplest form of the three-body problem is the restricted three-body problem (R3BP). This formulation is one of the most searched and interesting problem for astrophysicists and the problem defines the motion of an infinitesimal mass moving under the gravitational influence of two massive bodies which move in circular orbits around their common center of mass on the account of their mutual attraction. To tackle the problem of classical R3BP, Lagrange considered the behavior of the distances between the bodies without finding a general solution. He discovered two distinct classes of constant-pattern solutions in rotating frame of reference where gravitational equilibrium can be maintained. These points are called Lagrangian points (LPs) L_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$) and are very important in space missions (Szebehely [1]). A plethora of researches have been carried out by Abouelmagd et al [2, 3], Leke et al [4, 5], and Idrisi and Ullah [6] under different model formulations.

In view of the importance of Lagrangian points to the exploration and development of space, among the most fundamental questions about motion near equilibrium points are those about the existence of periodic orbits. Therefore, it is important to study the periodic structures around equilibrium points due to the rotational motion. Elements that could be used to describe the motion of the infinitesimal mass relative to the primary and secondary bodies are categorized as orbital and non-orbital elements. Angular momentum and total energy are the integrals available to measure the shapes and sizes of the orbits but may not be directly observable. Therefore, eccentricities, inclination and semi major axis of the orbits are used to determine the shapes, orientation and sizes of the orbits. Periodic orbits are also used as reference orbits. The study of periodic orbits is a very useful tool for the study of non-integrable dynamical system, because they determine critically the structure of phase space, while the study of periodic orbits, which are close to actual motions, plays an important role in understanding the general properties of such a system. Through the study of periodic orbits, one can understand the role of other forces besides gravitational forces. Moreover, the re-entry of artificial satellites has shown the importance of periodic orbits. Szebehely [1] gives a fairly good idea about the periodic orbits.

Many Mathematicians and Astronomers have investigated periodic orbits of the R3BP under different assumptions. Zagouras [7] considered the effect of radiation pressure on the periodic motion of small particle in the vicinity of the TLPs. Elipe and Lara [8] discussed periodic orbits in the R3BP by taking both the primaries as sources of radiation pressure. Perdios [9] studied critical symmetric periodic orbits in the photogravitational R3BP in which the first primary is a source of radiation, and the study was extended by Perdios and Kalantonis [10] when the first primary is an oblate spheroid. The investigation of the combined effect of perturbations, radiation and oblateness, on the periodic orbits in the neighborhood of linearly stable TLPs was carried out by AbdulRaheem and Singh [11]. The periodic orbits generated by Lagrangian solutions of the R3BP when one of

the primaries is an oblate body, was studied by Mittal et al. [12] while Abouelmagd and El-Shaboury [13] studied periodic orbits around the TLPs when the three bodies are oblate spheroids and the primaries are radiating. Singh and Haruna [14] examined the periodic orbits around TLPs of three oblate bodies under effect of radiation pressure of the primaries and small perturbations in the Coriolis and centrifugal forces. Singh and Leke [15] studied the periodic orbits when the main masses in the system are surrounded by a cluster of particles. Palacios et al. [16] investigated the symmetric periodic orbits in the Moulton-Copenhagen problem, while Abouelmagd et al [17] explored periodic solution of the nonlinear Sitnikov R3BP. Mittal et al. [18] studied the periodic orbits generated by Lagrangian solutions of the R3BP with non-spherical primaries, and, Leke and Singh [19] explored effects of perturbing forces on periodic orbits in the R3BP of three-oblate spheroids with circular cluster of material point.

The formulation of the classical R3BP assumes that the masses of primaries are constant. However, the phenomenon of absorption in stars inspired scientists to formulate the R3BP with variable mass(es). During evolution, the masses of celestial bodies change, particularly in a binary star system were mass changes rather rigorously. An interesting example of mass loss is the real physical scenario of those transiting exoplanets whose atmospheres are escaping because of the severe levels of energetic radiations, coming from their nearby parent stars, hitting them. Also, modern concepts of the change in the distance between the Earth and the Moon, and the change in their masses due to, out-gassing, impact of meteorites, asteroids, comets and space dust lead to the necessity of investigating dynamics problem in the Earth-Moon system under these conditions. It is believed that the Earth gains 100,000 kilograms of mass each year from space, one million kilograms of mass every day due to in falling meteors.

The R3BP with variable masses formulation is relevant in various astronomical and engineering contexts, such as, investigating the dynamics of spacecraft near asteroids or comets with variable masses due to surface outgassing. Investigating dynamics of binary stars with mass transfer between them and also studying dynamics in the Earth-Moon system during lunar mass discharge. Several authors such as Luk'yanov [20], Singh and Leke [21, 22, 23], Gao and Wang [24], Leke and Singh [25] and, Leke and Orum [26], have carried out interesting investigations of the variable mass R3BP under diverse characterizations.

Inspired by the vast applications of the R3BP with variable masses, and the deorbiting of NigComSat in 2007, we thought it timely to examine in this paper, investigations on instability of periodic orbits of NigComSat around TLPs in the R3BP with Radiation Pressure and Variable Masses

The importance of the study of the R3BP with variable mass R3BP is that the model provides a more accurate illustration of the real-world dynamics of celestial bodies and allows for more accurate dynamical predictions of their impending behaviors. For instance, the periodic orbits around the TLPs of the photogravitational R3BP studied by Zagouras [7] and may be inappropriate to discuss the model in the gravitational environment of a radiating body with varying masses. It is therefore, reasonable to generalize the study of the periodic orbit around triangular points of one radiating body by introducing mass variations of the bodies. The study will provide insights into the dynamical prediction on motion of the NigComSat in the Earth-Moon system.

The paper is organized in the following order: Section 2 contains the descriptions of the equations of motion and stability of the TLPs. Section 3 deals with the study of the periodic orbits. Here, the frequency and orientation of the elliptic orbits are computed analytically. The analytical computations have equally been backed up with numerical estimations in Section 4 while the conclusion is drawn in Section 5.

2 Descriptions of the Dynamical Equations and Stability of Triangular Lagrangian Points

The relative motion of the problem of two bodies with variable masses m_1 and m_2 is described by the equation

$$\ddot{\vec{r}} = -G \frac{(m_1 + m_2)}{r^3} \vec{r} \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) is similar to the equation of the classical problem of two bodies with constant masses, with the difference that now the sum of the masses is a certain function of time. Equation (1) is technically called the **Gylden-Mestschersky problem**(GMP) (Gylden,[27]; Mestschersky [28].

Mestschersky [28], reduced the GMP through the introduction of new variables and “time” to the equations of the classical problem of two bodies with constant masses by a transformation, which was thereafter known as the Mestschersky[28] transformation and is given as

$$x = \xi R(t), \quad y = \eta R(t), \quad z = \zeta R(t), \quad \frac{dt}{d\tau} = R^2(t) \\ r_i = \rho_i R(t), \quad (i=1,2), \quad r = \rho_{12} R(t) \quad (2)$$

where $R(t) = \sqrt{\alpha t^2 + 2\beta t + \gamma}$; ξ, η, ζ, τ are the new variables and ρ_{12} is constant.

Later, Mestschersky[29] came up with a law which considers the masses and their sum to vary in the same proportion in such a way that

$$\mu(t) = \frac{\mu_0}{R(t)}, \quad \mu_1(t) = \frac{\mu_{10}}{R(t)}, \quad \mu_2(t) = \frac{\mu_{20}}{R(t)} \quad (3)$$

where $\mu_1(t) = Gm_1(t)$, $\mu_2(t) = Gm_2(t)$, $\mu(t) = \mu_1(t) + \mu_2(t)$, μ_{10} and μ_{20} are constants.

The law (3) is called the Mestschersky unified law [29] (MUL)and it assures that the center of the mass of the system moves inertially.

Now, equation (1) has the particular solutions of the kinds:

$$\omega(t) = \frac{\omega_0}{R^2(t)}, \quad C^* = \rho_{12}^2 \omega_0, \quad r\mu = \kappa C^{*2}, \quad \kappa = \frac{\beta^2 - \alpha\gamma + \omega_0^2}{\omega_0^2} \quad (4)$$

where C^* is the constant of area integral.

Next, let m_1 and m_2 be the masses of two main bodies and let m_3 be the mass of the infinitesimal body. The equations of motion of the photo gravitational R3BP with smaller radiating body and variable masses are obtained from (Singh and Leke [21]) and are given by:

$$\ddot{x} - \dot{\omega}y - 2\omega\dot{y} = \omega^2 x - \frac{\mu_1(x-x_1)}{r_1^3} - \frac{\mu_2 q_2(x-x_2)}{r_2^3} \\ \ddot{y} + \dot{\omega}x + 2\omega\dot{x} = \omega^2 y - \frac{\mu_1 y}{r_1^3} - \frac{\mu_2 q_2 y}{r_2^3} \quad (5)$$

$$\ddot{z} = -\frac{\mu_1 z}{r_1^3} - \frac{\mu_2 q_2 z}{r_2^3}$$

where

$$r_1^2 = (x - x_1)^2 + y^2 + z^2, \quad r_2^2 = (x - x_2)^2 + y^2 + z^2, \quad x_1 = -\frac{\mu_2 r}{\mu_1 + \mu_2}, \quad x_2 = \frac{\mu_1 r}{\mu_1 + \mu_2}$$

r_1 and r_2 are the distances of the infinitesimal mass from the primaries positioned at $(x_1, 0, 0)$ and $(x_2, 0, 0)$, respectively, while μ_1 and μ_2 are the product of the masses of the primaries and the gravitational constant f . q_2 is the radiation pressure of the smaller primary, while ω is the angular velocity of the primaries. r is the distance between the primaries.

The equations of motion (1), in the autonomized system with constant coefficients have the forms (Singh and Leke [21]):

$$\xi'' - 2\eta' = \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial \xi}, \quad \eta'' + 2\xi' = \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial \eta}, \quad \zeta'' = \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial \zeta} \quad (6)$$

where,

$$\Omega = \frac{\kappa(\xi^2 + \eta^2)}{2} + \frac{(\kappa - 1)\zeta^2}{2} + \frac{\kappa(1 - \nu)}{\rho_1} + \frac{q_2 \kappa \nu}{\rho_2} \quad (7)$$

$$\rho_1 = \sqrt{(\xi + \nu)^2 + \eta^2 + \zeta^2}, \quad \rho_2 = \sqrt{(\xi + \nu - 1)^2 + \eta^2 + \zeta^2}$$

ν is the mass parameter and is such that $0 < \nu \leq \frac{1}{2}$, while κ is a constant of a particular integral of the GMP and

represents the random sum of the masses of the primaries and depicts the mass variation of the bodies in the autonomized system, and is such that $0 < \kappa < \infty$

Now, equations (6) admit the Jacobi integral

$$C + (\xi'^2 + \eta'^2 + \zeta'^2) = 2\Omega \quad (8)$$

where C is the Jacobi constant.

The equations of system (6) possess families of particular solutions-the relative Lagrangian states; five of which are analogous to the LPs of the classical R3BP and four additional LPs located outside the plane of motion on the $\xi\zeta$ - plane called out-of-plane LPs. In this paper, our aim is to explore instability of the periodic orbits and zero velocity curves (ZVC) of a Nigerian satellite (NigComSat) around linearly stable TLPs. In this premise, the location of the TLPs of the autonomized system (6) is obtained:

$$\xi = 1 - \nu - \frac{q_2^{2/3}}{2} \quad (9)$$

$$\eta = \pm \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{q_2^{2/3} (4 - q_2^{2/3})}$$

Equations (9) are the coordinates of the TLPs of the photo gravitational R3BP with variable masses. The coordinates (9) differ from those in Bekov [30] and Luk'yanov[20] only due to the radiation pressure force of the

smaller primary. Further, the points (9) differ from the location of the TLPs of Singh and Leke [21], due to the non-radiating force of the bigger primary.

Now, the TLPs (9) are stable when the roots of the characteristic equation

$$\lambda^4 - (\Omega_{\xi\xi}^0 + \Omega_{\eta\eta}^0 - 4)\lambda^2 + \Omega_{\xi\xi}^0\Omega_{\eta\eta}^0 - (\Omega_{\xi\eta}^0)^2 = 0 \quad (10)$$

are pure imaginary roots. Here the second order partial derivatives are computed at the TLPs and are such that

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{\xi\xi}^0 &= \frac{3\kappa}{4} \left[1 + \frac{4}{3}(1 - q_2) - 2\nu(1 - q_2) \right] \\ \Omega_{\eta\eta}^0 &= \frac{3\kappa}{4} \left[3 - \frac{4}{3}(1 - q_2) + 2\nu(1 - q_2) \right] \\ \Omega_{\xi\eta}^0 &= \frac{3\kappa\sqrt{3}}{4} \left[1 + \frac{4}{9}(1 - q_2) - 2\nu \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{9}(1 - q_2) \right\} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The characteristic equation (10) after substituting the partial derivatives (11) is

$$\lambda^4 + (4 - 3\kappa)\lambda^2 + \frac{3\kappa^2}{4}\nu(1 - \nu)[9 + 2(1 - q_2)] = 0 \quad (12)$$

Its roots are

$$\lambda_{1,2}^2 = \frac{3\kappa - 4 \pm \sqrt{D}}{2} \quad (13)$$

where D is the discriminant given by the equation,

$$D = 3\kappa^2[9 + 2(1 - q_2)]\nu^2 - 3\kappa^2[9 + 2(1 - q_2)]\nu + 9\kappa^2 - 24\kappa + 16 \quad (14)$$

Next, to establish the stability of the TLPs, there is the need to obtain the critical mass parameter, which is given by

$$\nu_{c\kappa} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{6\kappa} \sqrt{\frac{96\kappa - 9\kappa^2 - 64}{3}} - \frac{2(9\kappa^2 - 24\kappa + 16)(1 - q_2)}{27\kappa\sqrt{3}\sqrt{96\kappa - 9\kappa^2 - 64}} \quad (15)$$

Hence, when simultaneously $0 < \nu < \nu_{c\kappa}$, $D > 0$ and coefficient of λ^2 is positive, the value given by equation (13)

is negative. Hence, all the roots of the characteristic equation (12) are distinct pure imaginary and given as

$$\lambda_{1,2,3,4} = \pm s_i (i = 1, 2) \quad (16)$$

were

$$s_i = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(-P \pm \sqrt{D})}$$

$$P = 4 - 3\kappa$$

3. The Periodic Orbits

A dynamical system is periodic if the same configuration is repeated at regular intervals of time. Angular momentum and total energy are the integrals available to measure the shapes and sizes of the orbits but all these are not directly observable. Therefore, elements of the orbits such as eccentricities, inclination and semi major

axes of the orbits are used to determine the shapes, orientation and sizes of the orbits. In this section, we calculate the frequency, angle of inclination, eccentricity and lengths of the semi-axes, of the orbits.

3.1. Frequencies and Orientation of the orbits

When the roots are all distinct imaginary, motion is bounded and the TLPs are stable. The general solution when the roots are distinct pure imaginary values and motion is bounded is expressed as (Szebehely [1])

$$u = A_1 \cos s_1 \tau + A_2 \sin s_1 \tau + A_3 \cos s_2 \tau + A_4 \sin s_2 \tau \quad (17)$$

$$v = B_1 \cos s_1 \tau + B_2 \sin s_1 \tau + B_3 \cos s_2 \tau + B_4 \sin s_2 \tau$$

where the coefficients A_i and B_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) are the long and short periodic terms respectively, while s_1 and s_2 are the frequency of the long and short periodic orbits, respectively, and are obtained:

$$s_1 = \kappa \left[\frac{\nu(1-\nu)}{4-3\kappa} \left\{ \frac{27}{4} + \frac{3}{2}(1-q_2) \right\} \right]^{1/2} \quad (18)$$

$$s_2 = \sqrt{4-3\kappa} \left[1 - \frac{\kappa^2 \nu(1-\nu)}{(4-3\kappa)^2} \left\{ \frac{27}{4} + \frac{3}{2}(1-q_2) \right\} \right]^{1/2} \quad (19)$$

Eliminating the short periodic terms in equation (17), we have an elliptic orbit with long periodic terms given by

$$A_1 = \frac{1}{2} - \nu - \frac{1}{3}(1-q_2) \quad (20)$$

$$B_1 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \left[1 - \frac{2}{9}(1-q_2) \right]$$

$$A_2 = \frac{1}{3\kappa} \sqrt{\frac{4-3\kappa}{\nu}} \left[\frac{2}{3} - \frac{2}{3}\nu - \frac{\kappa\nu}{2(4-3\kappa)} + \frac{1}{27}(1-q_2) + \frac{\kappa^{1/3}}{9}(1-q_2) \right]$$

$$B_2 = -2\sqrt{\frac{4-3\kappa}{3\nu}} \left[\frac{1}{2} - \frac{3}{2}\nu + \frac{2\nu}{(4-3\kappa)} - \frac{3\kappa\nu}{8(4-3\kappa)} + \frac{1}{4}(1-q_2) + \frac{\kappa^{1/3}}{12}(1-q_2) \right]$$

The periodic terms for the short period orbit can also be analogously determined.

Now, we expand the potential around the triangular points to get

$$\Omega = \Omega^0 + \frac{1}{2}\Omega_{\xi\xi}^0 u^2 + \Omega_{\xi\eta}^0 uv + \frac{1}{2}\Omega_{\eta\eta}^0 v^2 + O(3) \quad (21)$$

where $O(3)$ represents the third and higher terms in u and v .

A symmetric form of the potential in equations (7) with $\zeta = 0$ is given by the equation

$$\Omega^0 = \frac{\kappa}{2} \left[(1-\nu)\rho_1^2 + \nu\rho_2^2 \right] + \frac{\kappa(1-\nu)}{\rho_1} + \frac{q_2\kappa\nu}{\rho_2} \quad (22)$$

Where;

$$\rho_1 = 1 \text{ and } \rho_2 = 1 - \frac{1}{3}(1 - q_2) \quad (23)$$

Substituting equations (23) in equation of (22), expressing $q_i = 1 - (1 - q_i)$ and simplifying, we get

$$\Omega^0 = \kappa \left[\frac{3}{2} - \nu(1 - q_2) \right] \quad (24)$$

Substituting equation (24) and the partial derivatives (11) in equation (21), and simplifying, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega = & \kappa \left[\frac{3}{2} - \nu(1 - q_2) \right] + \left[\frac{3}{8} + \left(\frac{2 - 3\nu}{4} \right) (1 - q_2) \right] u^2 + \sqrt{3}\kappa \left[\left(\frac{3}{4} - \frac{3\nu}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{2 - \nu}{6} \right) (1 - q_2) \right] uv \\ & + \kappa \left[\frac{9}{8} + \left(\frac{-2 + 3\nu}{4} \right) (1 - q_2) \right] v^2 \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Now, we introduce the variables \bar{u} and \bar{v} by the transformation

$$u = \bar{u} \cos \alpha - \bar{v} \sin \alpha, \quad v = \bar{u} \sin \alpha - \bar{v} \cos \alpha \quad (26)$$

which is equivalent to rotating the coordinate system through an angle α .

Factorizing and ignoring higher order terms in $(1 - q_2)$; we get the new quadratic form of (25), such that

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Omega} = & \kappa \left[\frac{3}{2} - (1 - \nu)(1 - q_1) - \nu(1 - q_2) \right] + \left(\frac{2 - 3\nu}{4} \right) (1 - q_2) \left[\bar{u}^2 \cos^2 \alpha + \bar{v}^2 \sin^2 \alpha - 2\bar{u}\bar{v} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \right] \\ & + \sqrt{3}\kappa \left[\left(\frac{3}{4} - \frac{3\nu}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{2 - \nu}{6} \right) (1 - q_2) \right] \left[(\bar{u}^2 - \bar{v}^2) \sin \alpha \cos \alpha + \bar{u}\bar{v} (\cos^2 \alpha - \sin^2 \alpha) \right] \\ & + \kappa \left[\frac{9}{8} + \left(\frac{-2 + 3\nu}{4} \right) (1 - q_2) \right] \left[\bar{u}^2 \sin^2 \alpha + \bar{v}^2 \cos^2 \alpha + 2\bar{u}\bar{v} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \right] \end{aligned}$$

Next, we select α such that the terms $\bar{u}\bar{v}$ is zero; we then use Binomial expansion and simplify, while ignoring products and higher order terms in $(1 - q_2)$; to get

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Omega} = & \kappa \left[\frac{3}{2} - \nu(1 - q_2) \right] + \kappa \left[\frac{3}{8} + \left(\frac{1 - 3\nu}{2} - \frac{3\nu}{4} \right) (1 - q_2) \right] \left[\bar{u}^2 \cos^2 \alpha + \bar{v}^2 \sin^2 \alpha \right] \\ & + \sqrt{3}\kappa \left[\frac{3}{4} - \frac{3\nu}{2} - \left(\frac{2 - \nu}{6} \right) (1 - q_2) \right] \left[(\bar{u}^2 - \bar{v}^2) \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \right] \\ & + \kappa \left[\frac{9}{8} + \left(\frac{-2 + 3\nu}{4} \right) (1 - q_2) \right] \left[\bar{u}^2 \sin^2 \alpha + \bar{v}^2 \cos^2 \alpha \right] \end{aligned}$$

Expanding, we get

$$\bar{\Omega} = \bar{u}^2 \bar{r} + \bar{v}^2 \bar{s} + \bar{t}$$

Where;

$$\bar{t} = \kappa \left[\frac{3}{2} - \nu(1 - q_2) \right]$$

$$\bar{r} = \kappa \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{3\nu}{4} \right) \cos 2\alpha + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{12} (-2 + \nu) \sin 2\alpha \right\} (1 - q_2)$$

$$\bar{s} = \kappa \left\{ \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{3\nu}{4} \right) \cos 2\alpha - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{12} (-2 + \nu) \sin 2\alpha \right\} (1 - q_2)$$

Now, setting the coefficient of uv to zero in equation (25), we subtract the coefficient of u^2 from those of v^2 and add it to terms of uv to get

$$\tan 2\alpha = \frac{4\sqrt{3}}{3} \left[\frac{3}{4} - \frac{3\nu}{2} + \left(\frac{4}{3} - \frac{11\nu}{3} - 3\nu^2 \right) (1 - q_2) \right] \quad (27)$$

Equation (27) gives the angle of orientation of the orbit and is analogous to those obtained by AbdulRaheem and Singh [11], Singh and Haruna [14] Leke and Singh [19].

3.2 Eccentricities of the orbits

The associated characteristic equation when the potential in equation (25) admits the Jacobi integral $J = 2\Omega$, is

$$\lambda^2 - (\Omega_{\xi\xi}^0 + \Omega_{\eta\eta}^0) \lambda + \Omega_{\xi\xi}^0 \Omega_{\eta\eta}^0 - (\Omega_{\xi\eta}^0)^2 = 0 \quad (28)$$

Substituting the partial derivatives (11) in equation (28), and simplifying, we get

$$\lambda^2 - 3\kappa\lambda + \frac{3\kappa^2\nu}{2} (1 - \nu)(1 - q_2) + \frac{27\kappa^2\nu(1 - \nu)}{4} = 0 \quad (29)$$

Its roots are

$$\lambda_1 = 3\kappa - \frac{9\kappa\nu(1 - \nu)}{4} - \frac{\kappa\nu}{2} (1 - \nu)(1 - q_2) \quad (30)$$

$$\lambda_2 = \frac{9}{4} \kappa\nu(1 - \nu) \left\{ 1 + \frac{2}{9} (1 - q_2) \right\} \quad (31)$$

With the help of the first root above, the eccentricities of the orbits can then be obtained following Szebehely [1]:

$$e_i = \sqrt{1 - \gamma_i^2}, \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (32)$$

$$\text{where } \gamma_i^2 = 4s_i^2 (s_i^2 + \lambda_i)^{-2}$$

Here, $s_i (i = 1, 2)$ are given in equations (18) and (19), respectively, while λ_i are the roots of the characteristic equation (28). Now, through some calculations, we get

$$e_1 = 1 - \frac{3\nu}{2(4 - 3\kappa)} + \frac{3\nu^2}{2(4 - 3\kappa)} \left[1 + \frac{3(3\kappa - 2)}{(4 - 3\kappa)} \right] - \left[\frac{\nu}{3(4 - 3\kappa)} - \frac{(15\kappa - 8)\nu^2}{\kappa^{2/3}(4 - 3\kappa)^2} \right] (1 - q_2) \quad (33)$$

and

$$e_2 = \frac{\sqrt{3\kappa}}{2} \left[1 + \frac{(153\kappa - 54\kappa^2 - 96)\nu}{8(4 - 3\kappa)} - \frac{(-108\kappa^2 + 306\kappa - 81\kappa^{1/3} - 192)\nu^2}{16(4 - 3\kappa)} - \frac{1}{6} \left\{ \frac{(8 - 9\kappa)\nu}{2(4 - 3\kappa)} + \frac{(9\kappa^{10/3} - 54\kappa - 36\kappa^{2/3} + 56)\nu^2}{4(4 - 3\kappa)^2} \right\} (1 - q_2) \right] \quad (34)$$

Equations (33) and (34) are the eccentricities of the long and short period orbits, respectively. These equations are defined by the mass parameter, the radiation pressure of the smaller primary and the mass variation parameter.

3.3 The semi-axes of the orbits

The lengths of the semi-major axes, a_i and the semi-minor axes, b_i of the long and short period orbits are obtained from the respective equations below:

$$a_i = \frac{1}{\delta_i} (\xi^2 \delta_i^2 + \eta^2)^{1/2}, \quad b_i = (\xi^2 \delta_i^2 + \eta^2)^{1/2}, \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (35)$$

where ξ and η are the location of triangular LPs (9).

Solving, we get

$$a_1 = \frac{\sqrt{(6\kappa - 1)}}{2} \left[1 - \frac{2\nu}{(6\kappa - 1)} + \frac{2\nu^2}{(6\kappa - 1)} + \frac{(4 - 3\kappa)}{2\nu(6\kappa - 1)} + \frac{2A_1(1 - q_2)}{3(6\kappa - 1)} \right] \quad (36)$$

where;

$$A_1 = \frac{1}{6}(3\kappa + 2) - 2\nu - \frac{(4 - 3\kappa)}{2}$$

Equation (36) gives the length of the semi-major axis of the long period orbits.

Similarly, the length of the semi-minor axis of the long period orbit gives

$$b_1 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\kappa^{1/3}} \left[1 + \frac{\nu\kappa^{2/3}}{2(4 - 3\kappa)} - \frac{\kappa^{2/3}(14 - 3\kappa^{4/3} - 3\kappa)\nu^2}{2(4 - 3\kappa)^2} + \left\{ \frac{2}{9} + \frac{7\kappa^{2/3}\nu}{9(4 - 3\kappa)} - \frac{\kappa^{2/3}(3\kappa - 44)\nu^2}{9(4 - 3\kappa)^2} \right\} (1 - q_2) \right] \quad (37)$$

Similarly, the length of the semi-major axis for the short period orbit is

$$a_2 = \frac{\sqrt{16 - 3\kappa}}{2\kappa^{1/3}\sqrt{4 - 3\kappa}} \left[1 + \frac{\kappa^{4/3}(378\kappa^3 - 945\kappa^2 + 288\kappa + 256)\nu}{2(27\kappa^3 - 216\kappa^2 + 432\kappa - 256)} + \frac{(1085\kappa^3 - 1602\kappa^2 - 1440\kappa + 108\kappa^{2/3} + 1728\kappa^{1/3} + 512)\nu^2}{4(9\kappa^2 - 24\kappa + 16)(16 - 3\kappa)} + \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{-4\kappa}{(16 - 3\kappa)} + \frac{2(540\kappa^3 - 108\kappa^{7/3} - 1269\kappa^2 + 1080\kappa - 256)\nu}{3(4 - 3\kappa)^2(16 - 3\kappa)} + \frac{3\kappa^{5/3}(29\kappa^{13/3} - 1134\kappa^4 + 4862\kappa^3 - 8010\kappa^2 + 6024\kappa + 192\kappa^{1/3} - 1984)\nu^2}{(4 - 3\kappa)^3(16 - 3\kappa)} \right\} (1 - q_2) \right] \quad (38)$$

Lastly, for the length of the semi-minor axis of the short period orbit, we get

$$b_2 = \frac{\sqrt{(16-3\kappa)}}{4} \left[1 - \frac{N_1 \nu}{8\kappa^{4/3}(16-3\kappa)(4-3\kappa)} + \frac{N_2 \nu^2}{16\kappa^{8/3}(16-3\kappa)(4-3\kappa)} \right. \\ \left. + \left\{ 2\kappa^{2/3}(4-3\kappa-4\kappa^{2/3}) + \frac{N_3 \nu}{2\kappa^{2/3}(4-3\kappa)} + \frac{3N_4 \nu^2}{4\kappa^{4/3}(4-3\kappa)} \right\} (1-q_2) \right] \quad (39)$$

Where;

$$N_1 = 603\kappa^{10/3} + 256\kappa^{4/3} - 162\kappa^{13/3} + 96\kappa^3 - 768\kappa^{7/3}$$

$$N_2 = -1863\kappa^{17/3} + 4590\kappa^{14/3} - 3648\kappa^{11/3} + 512\kappa^{8/3}$$

$$N_3 = 162\kappa^{13/3} - \frac{1089}{2}\kappa^{10/3} + 492\kappa^{7/3} - 128\kappa^{4/3}$$

$$N_4 = \frac{\kappa}{2(4-3\kappa)} \left[120\kappa^{5/3} - 54\kappa^{8/3} - 64\kappa^{2/3} - 27\kappa^5 \right] - 405\kappa^{11/3} + 954\kappa^{8/3} - 608\kappa^{5/3}$$

4. Numerical Applications

4.1 Periodic Orbits

In this section, we focus on the numerical applications of the study, for Earth-Moon-NigComSat system. For the mass parameter, we take $\nu = 0.01$ while the radiation pressure of the Moon is assumed to be $q_2 = 0.9986$. First, we compute numerically the locations of the triangular points given in equation (9) in Table 1. It is observed that the radiation pressure of the Moon causes a slight deviation. The graphs showing the slight change in the locations of the TLPs due to the radiation pressure of the Moon is shown in Fig 1. All numerical and graphical explorations have been carried out using the software Mathematica(Wolfram [31])

Table 1: Locations of TLPs of the NigComSat in the Earth-Moon System

$q_2 = 1$		$q_2 = 0.9986$	
ξ	$\pm \eta$	ξ	$\pm \eta$
0.49	0.866025	0.490467	0.865352

Fig 1: TLPs of the NigComSat in Earth-Moon System when (a) classical (b) photogravitational

Next, we compute numerical evaluations of the eccentricities of the long and short periodic orbits given in equations (33) and (34), respectively, for the NigComSat in the Earth-Moon system in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Eccentricity of the Long and Short Periodic Orbits of the NigComSat in the Earth-Moon System when $0 < \kappa < \infty$

κ	$q_2 = 1$		$q_2 = 0.9986$	
	e_1	e_2	e_1	e_2
0.000000001	0.996231	0.0000265728	0.92623	0.0000265727
0.1	0.995931	0.266437	0.995929	0.266437
0.5	0.994024	0.602468	0.994022	0.602467
1	0.985600	0.869679	0.985596	0.86968
1.001	0.985559	0.870173	0.985556	0.870174
1.2	0.967375	0.978839	0.967371	0.978848
1.227280	0.960802	0.999992	0.960800	1
1.227281	0.960802	0.999993	0.960800	1.00001
1.3	0.937000	1.13511	0.937088	1.13517
1.313702	0.999689	1.2481200	1	1.24826
1.313703	0.999702	1.2481400	1.00002	1.24827
4/3	DNE	DNE	DNE	DNE
1.34	4.01500	0.226594	4.01872	0.226886
1.35	1.66600	0.692758	1.66665	0.692746
1.8	1.01139	1.15682	1.01139	1.156820
2	1.00788	1.2289	1.00788	1.228890
10	1.00059	3.25546	1.00059	3.255450
39	1.00014	9.92518	1.00014	9.925150
40	1.00013	10.1736	1.0013	10.17360
341	1.00020	136.93	1.0002	136.9300
342	1.00010	137.488	1.0001	137.4880
1021	1.00010	656.09	1.0001	656.0900
1022	1	657.028	1	657.0260
$\kappa \rightarrow \infty$	1	$\kappa \rightarrow +\infty$	1	$\kappa \rightarrow -\infty$

Table 2 presents the eccentricities e_1 and e_2 of the long and short period orbits, respectively of the NigComSat in the gravitational field of the Earth and Moon. It is seen that the orbit of the NigComSat around TLP in the Earth-Moon system, when the radiation pressure is absent and present. Since eccentricity is the measure by how much an orbit departs from been circular, it is seen that the eccentricities of the long and short period orbits under effects of the radiation pressure of the Moon and the mass variation parameter are always less than one when the mass variation parameter is in the interval $0 < \kappa < 1.313702$ and $0 < \kappa < 1.227280$, respectively. Therefore, the orbits of NigComSat in this case are elliptical orbits. When $\kappa = 1.313702$ and $\kappa = 1.227280$ the long and short period orbits become parabolas, respectively. Further, the orbits soon become hyperbolas when $\kappa = 1.313703$ and $\kappa = 1.227281$, respectively. However, when the mass variation constant κ of the Earth and the Moon reaches

$\kappa = \frac{4}{3}$, the eccentricities do not exist (DNE) and consequently, the orbits collapse in this case. Further, as the mass variation constant increases to $\frac{4}{3} < \kappa < \infty$, the long period orbits of NigComSat change from hyperbolic to parabolic orbits while the short period orbits evolved from elliptical to parabolic and hyperbolas within these intervals. It is seen that the eccentricities of the long periodic orbits do not at any point tend to infinity even as the mass variation parameter tends to infinity.

Table 3: Lengths of the Semi-axes of Long and Short Periodic Orbits of the NigComSat in the Earth-Moon System for $q_2 = 0.9986$

κ	a_1	b_1	a_2	b_2
0.000000001	-1413.50i	866.295	1000.05	0.99505
0.1	-206.365i	1.86690	2.21857	0.988267
0.166	-1957.40i	1.57692	1.91308	0.982802
0.167	2765.90	1.57377	1.90988	0.982716
0.5	63.4898	1.09278	1.5104	0.950794
1	17.3864	0.87029	1.81968	0.891349
1.3	3.19459	0.81356	45.624	0.786909
1.32	2.39263	0.78000	430.704	0.670036
1.333	1.86578	DNE	DNE	DNE
1.34	1.60464	-0.11409	-2517.03i	1.21791
1.35	1.21571	0.583358	-266.4950i	1.00279
1.38	0.06845	0.730713	-25.1736i	0.904678
1.39	-0.30765	0.739114	-16.9294i	0.894056
5	-68.4122	0.505954	-0.699916i	0.0097268
6	-79.4839	0.476192	0.821134	0.481959i
10	-114.244	0.401750	0.725765	0.575556i
100	-410.285	0.186573	3.73217	-420i
$\kappa \rightarrow \infty$	$\rightarrow -\infty$	$\rightarrow 0$	$\rightarrow \infty$	Imaginary

The numerical computations in Table 3 represent the lengths of the semi-major $a_{1,2}$ and semi-minor axis $b_{1,2}$ of the long and short periodic orbit of the NigComSat in the field of the Earth and Moon. In the case of the semi-axis of the long period orbits, it is seen that for $0 < \kappa \leq 0.166$, the major axis of the orbits is imaginary and turns to real positive values when $0.167 \leq \kappa \leq 1.38$. The lengths become negative when the mass variation constant is in the interval $1.39 \leq \kappa < \infty$. In the case of the length of the minor axis of the long period orbits, the lengths are

positive throughout for $0 < \kappa < \frac{4}{3}$. The axis collapses when $\kappa = \frac{4}{3}$ and does not exist (DNE); and turns negative

when $\frac{4}{3} < \kappa \leq 1.34$. The lengths again turn positive when $1.35 \leq \kappa < \infty$. Hence, the major axis exists only when the

mass variation parameter is in the region $0.167 \leq \kappa \leq 1.38$, while the minor axis exists only when $0 < \kappa < \frac{4}{3}$ and

$1.35 \leq \kappa < \infty$. Additionally, it is observed that the lengths of the axes of the long periodic orbits decrease with increase in the mass variation parameter κ of the Earth and the Moon. Therefore, as the Earth and Moon gain more mass, the lengths of the major and minor axes of the long periodic orbits of the NigComSat decreases and reaches to a stage where they turn negative. Consequently, the orbits collapse and the NigComSat is likely to escape from orbit in this case.

In the case of the lengths of the major and minor axes of the short period orbits of NigComSat, it is seen from the Table 3, that the major axes are positive and real when the mass variation parameter is in the region $0 < \kappa < \frac{4}{3}$,

does not exist when $\kappa = \frac{4}{3}$ and turns imaginary when $\frac{4}{3} < \kappa \leq 5.99$. Interestingly, the lengths of the major axis

turn positive when the mass variation parameter is in the region $6 \leq \kappa < \infty$. Same analysis is followed for the minor axis of the short periodic orbits. Finally, we observe that as the mass variation parameter tends to infinity, the lengths of the major and minor axis of the long periodic tends to negative infinity and zero respectively, while the lengths of the axes of the short periodic orbits tends to infinity and imaginary values, respectively. We sum up our results as follows:

- i. In the case of negative, imaginary or zero lengths of the axes, this implies a collapse in the orbits of NigComSat
- ii. In the case of the axes tending to infinity, this means that the gravitational bound to keep the satellite in orbits around the TLPs may lose hold on the satellite.

From the two above presumptions, we conclude that the NigComSat is likely to escape from orbit.

Figures 2 to Fig 6 are the plots of the orbits of the NigComSat around triangular LPs in the gravitational field of the Earth and Moon.

Fig 2: Long periodic orbits of the NigComSat in the Earth-Moon System when (a) $\kappa = 0.167$ (b) $\kappa = 0.5$ (c) $\kappa = 1$ (d) $\kappa = 1.3$ (e) $\kappa = 1.33$ (f) $\kappa = 1.34$

Fig 3: Combined plot of long period orbits of the NigComSat around triangular LPs in the Earth-Moon System when $\kappa = 1$ (Red), $\kappa = 1.3$ (Blue) $\kappa = 1.33$ (Black)

Figures 2 are the plots of the long periodic orbits of NigComSat in the gravitational field of the Earth and a radiating Moon, for different mass variation parameter. From the graphs, it is seen the orientation and paths around the TLPs differ. From Fig 2a, it is observed that when $\kappa = 0.167$ the path of NigComSat around the Moon is semi-circular. In this case, the NigComSat doesn't travel around the TLPs neither does it orbit the Earth. As the mass variation parameter increases to 0.5, it is seen from Fig 2b that the NigComSat orbits the Earth and the TLP lying below the line joining the Earth and Moon. Further, as the mass variation increases to 1.3 and 1.33, the NigComSat only orbits the Earth as seen in Fig 2d&e. Afterwards, when the Earth and Moon gain more mass ($\kappa = 1.34$), the orbit flattens and the NigComSat does not orbit the Earth as seen in Fig 2f. Figure 3 is the combined

plots of the long periodic orbits of the NigComSat for different mass variation parameter. The red plot is the case when the mass variation parameter is a unit, while the blue and black orbits are the cases when the mass variation parameters are 1.3 and 1.33, respectively. This shows that the increasing masses of the Earth and the Moon induce instability on motion of NigComSat around its orbits and hence it leaves the orbit due to the instabilities posed by the increasing mass of the Earth and the Moon coupled with the radiation pressure of the Moon.

Fig 4: Short period orbit of NigComSat around TLPs in the Earth-Moon System when (a) $\kappa = 0.000000001$ (b) $\kappa = 0.5$ (c) $\kappa = 1$ (d) $\kappa = 1.2$

Fig 5: Short period orbits of NigComSat around TLPs in the Earth-Moon System when $\kappa = 0.000000001$ (red) (b) $\kappa = 0.3$ (blue) and $\kappa = 0.5$ (green)

Fig 6: Combined plots of the short period (green) and long period (red) orbits of the NigComSat around triangular LPs in Earth-Moon System when (a) $\kappa = 0.5$ (b) $\kappa = 1$

Fig 4 also shows the effect of the mass variation parameter κ on the short period orbits of the NigComSat around TLPs. It is seen from Fig4a-c that motion of NigComSat only takes places around the Earth and orbits the TLP when the mass variation parameter is 1.2 (Fig 4c).The combined plot to show the variations in the paths of the NigComSat around the short periodic orbits is given in Fig 5, while Fig 6 compares the plots of the long and short period orbits under effect of the mass variation. It is seen that the long periodic orbits of NigComSat around TLP exist when $0.167 \leq \kappa < \frac{4}{3}$, while those for the short period orbits exist for $0 < \kappa < \frac{4}{3}$ and paths around the TLPs do not exist outside these intervals.

4.2 Zero velocity curves around triangular points

For a given value of C, we can obtain the zero-velocity curves (ZVCs) around the TLPs of the photogravitational

R3BP with variable masses on the $\xi\eta$ -plane using equation (8) as shown in Figures 7 and 8. These figures demonstrate for various values of the energy constant how the region from which the NigComSat is dynamically prohibited and evolves as the value of the energy constant under radiation pressure together with random sum of the Earth and the Moon which is a measure of how the bodies gain or lose mass. We shall unveil where motion of the NigComSat is dynamically prohibited or allowed.

Fig 7: ZVCs of NigComSat around TLP in the Earth-Moon System for (a) $\kappa = 0.000000001$ & $C = 2.99 \times 10^{-9}$ (b) $\kappa = 5$ & $C = 14.9504$ (c) $\kappa = 10$ & $C = 29.9007$ and (d) $\kappa \rightarrow \infty$ & $C \rightarrow \infty$

The ZVCs of the NigComSat have been drawn under effects of mass variations of the Earth (black) and Moon (Yellow). The red region depicts the area where motion of the NigComSat is dynamically prohibited while the blue area is the region where the motion of the NigComSat is allowed. Figures 7a-d shows the effect of the mass variations of the Earth and Moon on the ZVCs of the NigComSat. It is seen in Fig 7a, that the NigComSat is free to travel around the Earth and Moon and the TLPs, and even to the exterior realm without any restrictions. However, such freedom becomes little restricted in Fig 7b&c, as the blue region decreases when the mass variation parameter increases. It is seen in Fig 7b, (when $\kappa = 5$), that motion of NigComSat is not permissible around the Earth but allowed around the Moon and the TLPs. Further, in Fig 7c, motion is not allowed around the Earth and the Moon but allowed around the TLPs. Finally, as the mass variation parameter tends to infinity, it is seen in Fig 7d that motion is not allowed around the Earth, Moon and the TLPs.

Fig 8: ZVCs of NigComSat around TLPs in The Earth-Moon System when $\kappa = 1$ and (a) $C = 2.76117$, $q_2 = 0.9986$ (b) $C = 2.76130$, $q_2 = 1$

Finally, Fig 8 shows the slight impact of the radiation pressure of the Moon on the ZVC of the NigComSat. It is observed that radiation pressure of the Moon decreases the region where motion of the NigComSat is allowed. Consequently, the increasing mass of the Earth and the Moon coupled with the radiation pressure of the Moon perturbs the motion of the NigComSat and induces instability. The likelihood of the NigComSat escaping from the vicinity of the TLPs is very high.

Therefore, we can conclude that the mass variation parameter plays the most active role in the region where motion of the NigComSat is allowed or prohibited.

5. Conclusion

The paper explored instabilities of periodic orbits of the Nigerian Communication Satellite (NigComSat) and zero velocity curves around triangular Lagrangian points using the model of the R3BP with variable masses and radiation pressure. For the triangular points of the autonomized systems, we computed explicit expressions for the frequency, angle of rotation of the principal axis, eccentricity and lengths of semi-major and minor axes of the orbits. Since some facts are not directly observable from the analytic solutions, numerical evidences was provided to analyze the structure and effect of the perturbing forces due to radiation and mass variations of the primaries on the elements of the orbits, in the Earth-Moon system. We gave the plots of the orbits of the NigComSat and found that for some value of the mass variation parameter, the orientations and path the

NigComSat travels around the Earth, the TLPs differs. Finally, the ZVCs around TLPs are explored and it is seen that the radiation pressure force decreases slightly the region where motion of the satellite is allowed, while the most significant perturbing effects is the mass variation parameter of the main bodies. When the Earth and the Moon keep gaining mass, large region becomes dynamically forbidden for the satellite and it is likely to leave the vicinity of the triangular points and escape into space. A question of celestial mechanics is how long could the TLPs may have restricted the NigComSat in orbit from escaping? The determination of ranges of semi-major axis taking into account the perturbing forces helped to know if the satellite is likely to remain or escape. It is seen that under effects of radiation and mass variation of the primaries, negative, imaginary or zero lengths of the axes, implies a collapse in the orbits of NigComSat and in the case when the axes are tending to infinity, this means that the gravitational bound to keep the satellite in orbits around the triangular LPs may lose hold on the satellite and the NigComSat is likely to escape from orbit.

The orbits about Lagrangian points are important for scientific investigations. Since, a number of space missions have been completed and some are being proposed by various space agencies.

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